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Rural Development Practices in SAARC Countries:

Some Innovative Cases

Written by: Dr. Rama Bashyal

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A Book Review

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The book “Rural Development Practices in SAARC Countries: Some Innovative Cases”, published in 2008, written by Rama Bashyal deals with rural development practices in the SAARC members nations (except Afghanistan) such as Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka. The publication presents these countries-specific some innovative rural development programmes specially focusing on income and employment generating activities in agriculture sector supported by rural financial institutions. This book has been prepared as an output of secondary data based study with an aim to acknowledge the significant steps taken for alleviating/reducing poverty in the region through sharing each other’s experiences and success stories of pro-poor poverty reduction strategies among the SAARC member nations.

This book is organised into four chapters. The first chapter reveals the introduction of South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) that includes its establishment, objectives, agreements declaration made in fifteenth summit and trade expansion. The second chapter discusses on the rural development which includes its concept, microfinance in the South Asia and microfinance promoted by the non-government organisations (NGOs).

In the third chapter, author deals with some innovative rural development practices in the SAARC counties. She presents country background of all member countries except Afghanistan followed by success stories of country-specific rural development programmes. Microfinance in Bangladesh is one of the successful practices for contributing in poverty alleviation of the rural areas. Professor Muhammad Yunus is a pioneer of Grameen Bank’s concept and promoted in the rural areas. It was initiated to target the Beggars in Bangladesh for powering them socio-economically. Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee (BRAC), one of the world’s largest NGOs, focused on, as a long-term issue, poverty alleviation and empowerment of the poor especially women and landless in the rural people to provide support in integrated. BRAC started to work in this approach since 1977 and its Rural

Development Programme (RDP) until 1989 had been working from 81 centres in 45 sub-districts of Bangladesh which are scattered over 22 of 64 districts with the total members 355,675.

Tourism industry has made significant contribution to the socio-economic development of Bhutan when the government privatised tourism sector in 1990. In starting (1974) government owned and run tourism industries in Bhutan but when government brought privatisation policy (1991) then rural tourism was promoted. Similarly, its Chukha Hydropower Project (CHP) (completed in 1988) generates 4 x 84 MW power and its 70 percent power is exported to India (West Bengal, Bihar, Jharkhand, Orisa, Sikkim, and Damodar Valley). CHP is the single largest source of the Bhutan Government (37 percent of total revenue).

Author has explained the experiences of India. Microfinance and Integrated Development Programmes have been proved as successful programmes in rural development of India. After its financial liberalisation, microfinance programmes contributed in poverty alleviation in the rural area. Indian government sponsored various poverty alleviation schemes such as Wage Employment and Infrastructure Development Programme, Self-Employment and Infrastructure Development Programme, Housing, Rural Water Supply and Sanitation Programmes, Programme for Rural Roads, Agricultural Marketing, Training and Research and Rural Technology. Likewise, Fishery is the second largest industry of Maldives and one of the successful models in the South Asia. A statistic shows that it is main source of the livelihood, single largest contributor in GDP which accounts for 11 percent of gross domestic product (GDP), 20 percent employment and 74 percent of the country's export commodities (which is the biggest source of foreign currencies).

Microfinance programme is also a successful poverty reduction measures in rural development of Nepal. This programme was started in 1956 through Credit Cooperatives in

Rapti Valley of Chitwan district to provide saving –credit services in Rural the rural area. Now, existing models in this sector are – (1) Government-Mandated Model, (2) Grameen Model, (3) Cooperative Model, (4) Financial Intermediary NGO/INGO/Donor Model (5) Apex Microfinance Institutions (e.g. Rural Microfinance Development Centre (RMDC), Sana Kisan Bikas Bank (SKBB) (Small Farmer Development Bank) and Rural Self-reliance Fund (RSRF). Pakistan’s community development programmes are successful examples in the South Asia. The Aga Khan Rural Support Programme (AKRSP), (started in 1989) has been supported the villagers to form village organisations (VOs) and investment in productive infrastructure based on the communities’ needs and demand. Likewise, Orangi Pilot Project (OPP) has been running in Karachi and Lahore, which are major cities of Pakistan, based on two principles i.e. shared rights and joint responsibilities for any social contract between government and citizens. The government’s role is to complement people’s work by providing larger facilities like water supply in college/university hospitals.

Rural development practices in Sri Lanka are found success in the sector of microfinance, agriculture and rural infrastructure development. The SANASA (Saving – credit) movement is a grassroots level financial intermediary organisation, which represents a cooperative approach to community empowerment and mobilisation of all ethnic communities to be active members. This movement has had over a century (since 1906) as an indigenous finance in Sri Lanka. Irrigation related Gal Oya Programme (from Gal Oya River) is successful project which commanded about 65,000 acres land. Moneragala Integrated Rural Development Project (2000-2005) brought visible changes in Sri Lanka in rehabilitation and upgrading of irrigation schemes in community development.

In the last chapter, author has summarised the whole discussion and drawn the conclusion based on the discussion made in the third chapter. Author emphasis is that agriculture sector that absorbs labour technologies (that provides employment opportunities

to the more than 60 percent of the population in each country) and it is an also appropriate technology. Besides, strengthen of agriculture sector is only the way for overall development of the rural area however it has so many constraints like lack of rural infrastructure.

Author emphasises that agriculture is a back-bone of all SAARC countries and its development is necessary as well as also important for rural development of these countries. This book mainly highlights the rural poverty alleviation aspect of the SAARC countries. Microfinance programmes were found more successful both programmes and means of poverty alleviation. Then agriculture sector including irrigation and other infrastructure development for development was also found successful sector of development. Besides, fishery, rural tourism and hydropower projects are also successful project in a country specific. Main reasons behind the success of all programmes are government's initiative role (investment in infrastructure development) and communities' management role. It is learnt that in the need or demand based and participatory approach, government should build infrastructure, support from backside (secondary role). Government's enforcement and commitment to support (initially key role then gradually reducing role and after certain time no role or only monitoring role) is very important for rural development. Oppositely, for certain time public-private partnership approach could be effective for some sectors like hydropower development and rural tourism. Bottom-up participatory development approach (Robert Chambers' – "Putting the Last First" principle) would be the one of the best approach in South Asian context because of existence of diverse socio-cultural structure and social exclusion or discrimination. That approach would be very effective not only addressing the social exclusion issues or diversity but also result-oriented development and sustainability of each development effort through creating social harmony, unity, peace and social justice.

Author does not discuss on government's policy while sharing success stories. Without government's clear and visionary policy and initiatives there is no chance or less

chance of getting success in a country's development. Definitely, each government has own policy and takes initiation either from its own side, or creates environment and promotes private sectors or and communities, or public-private partnership approach, or and opens-off to the non-government sectors (e.g. NGOs). That has to be discussed in the book. One of the important learning from this discussion is community empowerment, institutionalisation and its strengthening which core of the success of community development. On the other hand integrated rural development is also best way of rural development that includes all aspects of the community but, in practical, it is complex and we can find so many constraints like resource limitation, lack of continuation, effects of political instability, different issues raised by different interest groups, lack of expertise etc. But it is possible if it is launched strategically and proceeded step by step. Commitment of the government and political parties, and role support of NGO sector and international donor agencies, civil societies and citizens' own role are equally important.

Civil society and NGO sector should play facilitation role to make aware the communities and make responsible and accountable the government. Government should have clear vision, policy and action for own county's development and prosperity of the own citizens. At current situation, rights-based approach has been introduced in the development sector. Promotion of this approach will contribute to know citizens' own rights and realise and try to hold it that ultimately (in long term) helps in sustainability of the development. SAARC's one of the objectives (charters) is mutual cooperation in of each other's development. Author does not discuss about this concern which is also important part that needs to be analysed here while discussing regarding the SAARC's development practice. She mentions the introduction of the SAARC and then practices of the region rather discusses its role in the development of the member countries. For example, in Chukha Hydropower Project (CHP), Bhutan's the first mega power project, for which Government of India

provided 60 percent grants and 40 percent loan in 5 percent interest for 15 years. On the other hand, India purchased power generated from the same project for West Bangal, Bihar, Jharkhand, Orisa, Sikkim and Damodar Valley. That power has been contributing in the overall development of these regions.

Nepal has huge endowment of natural resources. Some of the good indicators have been observed in the rural development of Nepal. On one hand, it has to be continued. On the other hand, we have to make effort to apply lessons whatever we learnt from other neighbour countries but that should be contextualised in our context. Government's policy and initiation is should be clear and practicable, and other parties should play significant role at own level. Development is only possible through mutual efforts never ever only by one's effort.

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